

Special Group – Signatories of the Declaration “Towards access to at least 1 million sequenced genomes in the EU by 2022”

1+MG Group

3rd meeting

19 October 2021

(videoconference)

Legal basis for secondary use of data in 1+MG

(for information – agenda item 3a)

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4 October 2021

Regina Becker on behalf of Beyond One Million Genomes Project, Work Package 2

Background / Context

The aim of this document is to analyse the legal basis under the GDPR for secondary use of personal data in the 1+MG and give recommendations for the national / European implementation of 1+MG. Secondary use means here the processing of 1+MG data by data users for the purposes of research, healthcare and policy development. Our assumption is that data has been collected in a healthcare or research context or is part of a genomic initiative in the country. These data are then subsequently made available for secondary use in the European 1+MG cross-border infrastructure. This document does not discuss the rules for further processing under the GDPR. We will discuss these in a separate document. The legal aspects of data submission to 1+MG, the hosting, data discovery and data access provision will be subject to an independent discussion.

The requirements regarding the legal basis for processing health and genetic data for secondary use vary from country to country in Europe. In principle, the relevant options under Art. 6 are consent, public interest and legitimate interest. However, additional legitimation is required under Art. 9(2) for the processing of special category (health and genetic) data. The relevant options for a legitimation are either consent or national / European law. Relevant for 1+MG are Art. 9(2)(g), reasons of substantial public interest, 9(2)(h) around healthcare provision and management, 9(2)(i), public interest in the area of public health, and 9(2)(j), scientific research. Not all countries in the EEA have implemented all options available in Art 9(2) in the national legislative framework. Where the options for processing special categories of data have been implemented, these can be limited to certain stakeholders (e.g. public bodies in general or even defined institutions) or to a defined processing context (e.g. research in the public interest for Art. 9(2)(j)). Note that Art. 9(4) allows EEA Member States to further restrict the processing of health and genetic data, including restricting the available legal basis/legitimation.¹

Where northern European countries tend to rely more on public interest in the context of secondary use, the southern European countries have a strong focus on consent as the preferred legal basis and legitimation for processing health and genetic data in secondary use contexts.² In the following the different available legal bases will be analysed.

¹ Examples: France: Article 75

In the case where the search requires the examination of genetic characteristics, the informed and express consent of the persons concerned must be obtained prior to the implementation of the data processing. This article does not apply to research carried out pursuant to Article L. 1131-1-1 of the Public Health Code.

² Olga Tzortztaou et al., Biobanking Across Europe Post-GDPR: A Deliberately Fragmented Landscape. In: GDPR and Biobanking Individual Rights, Public Interest and Research Regulations across Europe, Law, Governance and Technologie series, Vol. 43, p. 397 -420, Springer Editions (2021)

Consent (Art. 6(1)(a))

Consent as a legal basis under the GDPR is required to be freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous and should be based on a clear affirmative action.³ Specific and unambiguous means in particular that the purposes need to be precise enough to inform on the necessary processing and that different purposes need to be consented for separately. Informed means that material information must be provided, including the identity of the controller⁴. Freely given includes that no significant advantages (or rather disadvantages when not consenting) should be connected to the consent and there should be no imbalance between the controller and the data subject⁵. It is an intrinsic element of consent as legal basis that it can always be withdrawn by the data subject, in which case the processing must cease unless there is another legal basis in place for a different purpose that requires continued processing (such as for continued storage).⁶ This means that consent is not a good legal basis where data need to be sustained, e.g. in archiving for reproducibility reasons.

While recital (33) provides some manoeuvring for scientific research as it allows consent to be given for the purposes of areas of research (also colloquially called following the ethics terms “broad consent”), it does not lift the requirement of recital (42), requiring the consent information to include the identity of the controller. This can naturally be interpreted to mean that a consent to processing for areas of research only applies to the controller obtaining the consent and any recipients explicitly mentioned in the consent form. However, these recitals are non-binding. Nowhere in the binding articles of GDPR is it mentioned that a consent is only informed if the identity of the controller(s) is mentioned. The consent articles only require the purpose(s) of the processing to be known. Therefore, it can alternatively be argued that where a data subject consents to processing for the purpose of areas of research, it is sufficient to mention categories of recipients in order for consent to serve as a [legitimate] legal basis also for downstream controllers.

The question has been submitted by the European Commission (EC) to the European Data Protection Board (EDPB)⁷ but has not yet been answered, so the matter remains open. Even if the EDPB provides guidance on this matter, the legislators in the different countries may interpret the requirement that consent be informed differently. Some countries are likely to insist that the identity of each controller relying on consent as a legal basis for secondary use be specified. This would mean that 1+MG data users would generally have to obtain a fresh consent for secondary use in these given countries. This insistence on specifying each controller is even more likely in the context of secondary use for healthcare or policy development purposes, as no broad consent is foreseen by the GDPR for these purposes.

³ GDPR Art. 4(11)

⁴ Recital (42)

⁵ Detailed information can be found in the EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679, https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-052020-consent-under-regulation-2016679_en

⁶ EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679

⁷ EDPB Document on response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_replyec_questionnairesearch_final.pdf

Requiring a fresh consent for each secondary use (dynamic consent), however, will not be feasible as it will likely lead to massive delays in response times, significant burden on data providers, and high attrition rates⁸, leading to heterogeneous collections with selection biases and massive logistic challenges. Countries that rely traditionally on a public interest legal basis in secondary use such as Finland⁹ will see little benefit in shifting to consent as a legal basis for secondary use.

This again means that a number of countries will rely on alternative legal bases to include the data, closing therefore the path to consent as downstream legal basis. In consequence, consent cannot be a mandatory homogeneous legal basis for secondary use in the 1+MG.

Countries relying traditionally on consent as legal basis for processing health and genetic data for research will either have a very limited scope of available data in 1+MG or have to rely on exceptional mechanisms to waive the consent requirement. Indeed, most countries relying strongly on consent have alternative pathways such as via approval procedures where it must be justified by the data controller why obtaining consent is impossible. However, in 1+MG it could be argued that where datasets are included with the option to maintain the link to the data subjects, either for exercising data subjects' rights, re-contacting for incidental findings, inclusion into prospective studies or clinical trials as well as longitudinal data collections and data linkage, re-consenting should likewise be possible. This would require logistics from all countries though and would come with the above-mentioned disadvantages.

1+MG data users from consent-focussed countries will have the burden of obtaining consent through specific mechanisms provided by the national / local nodes in 1+MG. More specifically, in those cases where the data controller cannot obtain the data subject's consent for a different process than the original one or where there may not have been a consent in the first place, studies have shown that in most countries, there are nationally regulated procedures in place, which lawfully permit the retrospective data processing (e.g. procedures which require that data controllers obtain, prior to secondary use of previously collected data, a certain authorization/approval from a competent body such as a Research Ethics Committee or Data Protection Authorities).¹⁰ 1+MG will likely need to verify that 1+MG data users have a legal basis available under both Art. 6(1) and 9(2). Such "verification mechanisms" can be particularly relevant where e.g. the mandate for data processing in the context of policy development is only defined around the access of national data resources or where the implementation of Art 9(2)(j) in national law is limited to research in the public interest. Depending on the implementation of this requirement, this might exclude private entities from secondary data access.

⁸ See e.g. Wallace et al., *Respecting Autonomy Over Time: Policy and Empirical Evidence on Re-Consent in Longitudinal Biomedical Research: Respecting Autonomy Over Time*, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276146811_Respecting_Autonomy_Over_Time_Policy_and_Empirical_Evidence_on_Re-Consent_in_Longitudinal_Biomedical_Research_Respecting_Autonomy_Over_Time

⁹ See e.g. Finnish Data Protection Act, Section 4 or the Act on Secondary Use of Health and Social Data.

¹⁰ Cf. the study *Assessment of the EU Member States' rules on health data in the light of GDPR*. DG Food and Health Safety, 2021, https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/default/files/ehealth/docs/ms_rules_health-data_en.pdf.

Task in the public interest (Art. 6(1)(e))

The public interest legal basis is a suitable one for medical research as stated by the EDPB¹¹ as well as the European Data Protection Supervisor¹² and could also serve well for secondary use in healthcare and policy development, in particular where public bodies will be responsible for the processing. To rely on public interest as a legal basis¹³, the basis of the processing has to be laid down in either the European or the Member State law to which the data user is subject¹⁴. This means, the task should be part of the mission given to a public body by law or a private body may be exercising a task that was established by law. This may cover private bodies operating in healthcare as well as private bodies supporting governmental policy development. However, the processing of health and genetic data for the respective tasks also need to have a legitimation through the implementation of Art 9(2) options in EU or national legislation (see above). Even where such implementations have been made, legislative authorisation may be limited to certain entities or processing contexts, and other limitations can be introduced via Art. 9(4). A legal basis under 6(1)(e) is therefore currently not open to all types of entities or all types of secondary use envisaged by 1+MG in all countries.

Legitimate interest (Art. 6(1)(f))

To rely on Art. 6(1)(f), where processing is necessary for purposes of legitimate interest of the controller, the entity needs to demonstrate in a balancing test that its own interest outweighs the interests and fundamental rights of the data subject. This could in principle be established for precision medicine purposes where pseudonymised data are processed under appropriate technical measures and safeguards and with a high level of transparency. However, similarly to Art. 6(1)(e), Art. 6(1)(f) needs to be also paired with an Art. 9(2) legitimation for the processing of health and genetic data, and therefore the limitations under Art. 9(4) are likely to apply.

An additional limitation is that legitimate interest is not available for public authorities in the performance of their tasks. Therefore, Art. 6(1)(f) is not suitable as a default legal basis. Even as a complement, Art. 6(1)(f) cannot make up for limitations in scope that preclude reliance on Art. 6(1)(e) by some public authorities.

Conflicting Implementations

The possible legal bases for secondary use by the user are established through the national legislation where the user as the territorial scope of data protection legislation is typically defined by the location of the controller or processor. However, some countries have additional criteria (DE, PT, FR) based on the location of the processing or the residence of the data subject. Due to the federated setup of the 1+MG, the applicable data protection law may therefore be ambiguous or overlapping as also related to the location of the data

¹¹ See e.g. EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679

¹² EDPS, Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research, https://edps.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publication/20-01-06_opinion_research_en.pdf

¹³ Art 6(1)(e)

¹⁴ Art. 6(3)

or the data subject. Diverging implementations of legal bases are likely in these circumstances to seriously hamper cross-border secondary use. Controllers may be hesitant to use data that have to be processed under a different legal framework, which they are little, or not at all, familiar with. In particular, where consent is the required legal basis for the secondary use processing in 1+MG independent of the location of the controller, these data are not likely to be selected by users who would otherwise be able to process e.g. based on public interest due to their own national legislative framework. As such, data in countries that impose their own legal data protection framework and required legal basis will be disadvantaged and may be effectively excluded from large parts of the processing with 1+MG.

Where data use is pursued through consortia, it also means that the same project may have to be performed under different legal bases depending on the location of the consortium partners.

This leads subsequently to inconsistent application of data subjects' rights. The European Data Protection Board has therefore recommended in their "Document on response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research" that whenever possible, the same legal basis should be used within a project.

Recommendation

As illustrated above, consent is not an appropriate mandatory legal basis to legitimate secondary use. This has been confirmed for the similar set-up of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) by the European Data Protection Supervisor in his Preliminary Opinion 8/2020. The recommendation of the EDPS is to consider public interest as a legal basis.

We would follow this recommendation because legitimate interest is excluded for relevant stakeholders who need access to the data. The purposes of 1+MG are well suited to justify such public interest. Public interest as homogeneous legal basis will also resolve the situation of different legal bases applying to the same data use depending on the location of user and/or data. However, to actually build on public interest as a legal basis requires legislation either on the European level or through each Member State who wants to engage in 1+MG. A European solution seems more practicable. However, reliance on European legislation creating a public interest and defining safeguards under Art. 89(1) would not overrule any additional safeguards for processing genetic /health data implemented by specific Member States under Art 9(4). These would have to be revoked for processing in the context of data use in 1+MG.

The legislative framework for data use could be provided for by the planned European Regulation for the EHDS, depending on the scope of processing that will be covered. This would be the easiest solution, though it is expected that also this Regulation will not provide any short-term solutions.

In the meantime, certainly those countries that have established the necessary legislative framework providing a public interest basis and legitimation for the processing of health

and genetic data for secondary use in healthcare, research and policy development will have a competitive advantage. The countries where such options are not or only partly established may want to think about bridging solutions that remedy gaps in the legislative coverage, e.g. where implementations of the Art. 9(2) clauses do not or only partly cover the envisaged scope of data use in 1+MG. Where countries only permit consent as a legal basis for secondary use together with potential waivers based on approval procedures, they may want to consider an exemption for 1+MG data use or at minimum a simplified approval process.

